

Kuweka wavu Neti ya Mbu

Mosquito Net Screening

- 1** Vichungi vya Flymesh huzuia kuingia kwa mbu /
Flymesh screens block mosquito entry
- 2** Hewa inaweza kupita kupitia kichungi, kusaidia
kudumisha hali ya joto nzuri ndani / Air can
flow through the screen, helping keep the inside
comfortable

Recessed window

Horizontal fixed shade

Vertical movable shade

Vertical fixed shade

Awning

Exterior operable shade

Bahama shutter

Trellis

Perforated horizontal overhang

Vegetation on window

Shrubs and tree shade

1

2

Kupunguza Msongamano

Reducing Overcrowding

- 1 Msongamano hurahisisha mbu kuuma watu kadhaa kwa sababu wako karibu karibu / Overcrowding makes it easier for a mosquito to bite several people because they**
- 2 Kutoa maeneo mengi ya kusubiri, ndani na nje, kunaweza kusaidia kupunguza msongamano / Providing multiple waiting areas, inside and outside, can help reduce overcrowding.**

Makazi ya Wanyama Wanaokula Mbu

Mosquito Predator Habitats

- 1** Wanyama fulani, ikiwa ni pamoja na baadhi ya ndege, popo, samaki, wadudu na amfibia hula mbu na viluwilwi vyao. / Certain animals, including some birds, bats, fish, insects and amphibians eat mosquitoes and their larvae.
- 2** Maeneo ya kijani, kama vile mabwawa, miti na mimea, yanaweza kusaidia kutoa makazi kwa wanyama hawa. / Green spaces, such as ponds, trees and plants, can help provide habitats for these animals.
- 3** Makazi yaliyotengenezwa na binadamu, kama vile maboksi ya ndege na maboksi ya popo, pia yanaweza kusaidia. / Man-made habitats, like bird boxes and bat boxes, may also help.
- 4** Ni muhimu kwamba maeneo haya yatunzwe vizuri kuzuia kuzaliana kwa mbu / It is important that these spaces are well looked-after to prevent mosquito breeding.

Vyandarua

Bednets

- 1** **Vyandarua hulinda watu wanaolala chini yake dhidi ya mbu / Bednets protect people sleep under them from mosquitoes.**
- 2** **Ni muhimu kuwa na nafasi ya kutosha ndani ya chandarua ili usiguse kando, kwani mbu anaweza kuuma kupitia hapo. / It is important there is enough room in the bednet to not touch the edges, as a mosquito could bite through it.**
- 3** **Vyandarua vinaweza kuwa na joto lisilo la starehe kuwa ndani yake. Weka chumba baridi kwa kutumia vivuli, uingizaji hewa na vifaa vya kupunguza joto. / Bednets can be uncomfortably hot to be inside. Keep the room cool using shading, ventilation and fans.**
- 4** **Vifaa vya kupunguza joto ndani ya chandarua pia vinaweza kusaidia kuifanya iwe baridi / Fans inside the bednet can also help keep it cool.**

MOSQUITO LARVA

1

2

2

2

Kuondoa Maji Yaliyosimama

Removing Standing Water

1 Mbu hutaga mayai yao kwenye maji yaliyosimama /
Mosquitoes lay their eggs in standing water.

2 Maji huwa yanakusanyika katika vyombo vya nje, vyombo vya mimea, mapipa ya taka, matairi, ndoo, makopo ya rangi, mifuniko, taka na mifereji ya paa. Kwa kuondoa au kumwaga hivi, unaweza kuzuia mbu kuzaliana ndani yake / Water commonly collects in outdoor containers, plant pots, bins, tires, buckets, paint cans, lids, trash and roof gutters. By removing or emptying these, you can prevent mosquitoes from breeding in them.

Kuboresha Milango

Improve Doors

- 1** Milango iliyo wazi na milango yenye nafasi kando inaweza kutengeneza njia za kuingia kwa mbu / Open doors and doors with gaps around the edges can create entry points for mosquitoes.
- 2** Vifaa vya kujifunga vyenyewe vinaweza kusaidia kuweka milango imefungwa / Self closing devices can help keep doors closed.
- 3** Brashi za mlango zinaweza kuziba nafasi kati ya sakafu na chini ya mlango / Door brushes can block the gap between the floor and the bottom of the door.
- 4** Milango yenye vichungi huboresha mzunguko wa hewa huku ikidumisha faragha / Screened doors improve airflow while maintaining privacy.

Kuboresha Matanki ya Maji Taka

Improving Septic Tanks

- 1 Matanki ya maji taka yana maji chini ya ardhi ambayo yametumika katika jengo kwa shughuli kama vile kuosha au kufurisha vyoo. Ikiwa mbu wanaweza kuingia, wanaweza kutaga mayai yao hapa. / Septic tanks contain water underground that has been used in the building for activities like washing or flushing toilets. If mosquitoes can enter, they can lay their eggs here.**
- 2 Vifuniko vya ukaguzi vya kudumu, visivyo na nafasi, huzaia mbu kuingia / Durable inspection hatches, without gaps, prevent mosquitoes entering.**
- 3 Kuweka vichungi kwenye mifereji ya uingizaji hewa pia kuzuia mbu kuingia / Screening ventilation pipes with flymesh also prevents mosquitoes entering.**
- 4 Tabaka la mipira ya polystyrene ndani ya tanki la maji taka linaweza kuzuia viluwilwi vya mbu kutoka. / A layer of polystyrene balls inside the septic tank can prevent mosquitoes larvae from escaping.**

Usimamizi wa Taka Uliofunikwa

Covered Waste Management

- 1** Taka ambayo haijafunikwa au isiyo katika mapipa yenye vifuniko inaweza kuwa maeneo ya kuzaliana mbu baada ya mvua / Trash that is not covered or in bins with lids can become mosquito breeding sites after rain.
- 2** Mapipa ya taka yenye vifuniko vilivyoinama huzuia maji ya mvua kuingia kwenye taka. / Trash bins with sloped lids keep rain water away from trash.
- 3** Vibanda vya mapipa hutoa ulinzi wa ziada dhidi ya mvua / Shelters for bins provide additional protection from rain.

Kivuli kwa Kupanda Mimea

Shading with Planting

- 1** Kupanda mimea karibu na majengo husaidia kuyaweka baridi. Hii inaweza kufanya iwe rahisi zaidi kuweka madirisha yenye wavu yafungwe na kutumia chandarua / Planting around buildings helps to keep them cool. This can make it more comfortable to keep screened windows closed and use a bednet.
- 2** Mimea inayopanda juu ya kuta inaweza kukuzwa kwa ajili ya kivuli / Climbing plants can be grown up walls for shade.
- 3** Paa za kijani zilizopandwa mimea hupunguza joto kutoka kwa jua ndani / Planted green roofs reduce warming from the sun inside.
- 4** Sehemu za kijani ni baridi zaidi kuliko sakafu ya zege / Green surfaces are cooler than concrete paving.

Usafi wa Mara kwa Mara

Regular Clean Up

- 1 Taka inaweza kwa urahisi kuwa maeneo ya kuzaliana mbu baada ya mvua / Trash can easily become mosquito breeding sites after rainfall.**
- 2 Kusafisha taka mara kwa mara huondoa maeneo haya yanayoweza kuzalisha mbu / Regularly cleaning up trash removes these potential mosquito breeding sites.**

Milango ya Kuingia ya Vestibule

Vestibule Entrances

- 1** Kuwa na milango miwili kati ya nje na ndani hutoa ulinzi bora zaidi dhidi ya mbu kuingia jengo / Having two doors between the outside and inside offers better protection against mosquitoes entering a building.
- 2** Ikiwa mlango mmoja utaacha wazi kwa bahati mbaya, mlango mwingine bado hutoa ulinzi / If one door is accidentally left open, the other door still provides protection.

Kuboresha Ufyonzaji wa Maji Ardhini

Improve Ground Water Absorption

- 1** **Sehemu ambazo hazifanyi maji kufyonzwa ardhini zinaweza kuunda maeneo ya kuzaliana baada ya mvua / Surfaces that do not allow water to soak into the ground can create breeding sites after rain.**
- 2** **'Soakaways' ni mashimo yaliyojazwa na mawe. Hii inaweza kusaidia maji kufyonzwa tena ardhini / 'Soakaways' are holes fills with rocks. This can help water soak back into the ground.**
- 3** **Sakafu ya 'kijani' inayoruhusu maji kupita pia husaidia ardhi kufyonza maji / Permaeable 'green' paving also helps the ground absorb water.**
- 4** **Miti na mizizi yake inaweza kusaidia ardhi kufyonza maji vizuri zaidi / Trees and their roots can help ground absorb water better.**